

Kinetic Isotope Effect Studies in the Oxidation of Benzhydrols by Hexavalent Chromium in Absence and in Presence of Oxalic Acid

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Kinetic deuterium isotope effect studies have been made on the oxidation of a number of benzhydrols by potassium dichromate both in absence of and in presence of oxalic acid. The substituent effect on the kinetic isotope effect as also the temperature effect on the kinetic isotope effect have been analysed and the structure and geometry of the transition state of these reactions have been delineated. The reactions exhibit a considerably lowered k_H/k_D values in the presence oxalic acid indicating a direct transition from Cr^{VI} to Cr^{III} in the cooxidation reaction. Added 2-hydroxy-2-methylbutyric acid (HMBA) fails to increase the rate of oxidation of benzhydrol by Cr^{VI} .

THOUGH kinetic isotope effect (KIE) studies have generally been employed as a mechanistic tool in the oxidation of alcohols by chromium(VI)^{1,2} detailed investigations have not been directed towards two aspects of this problem. These are the effects of substituents on the magnitude and direction of KIE and the temperature dependence of KIE. The latter effect (TDKIE) has been used as valuable tool to understand the nature of the hydrogen transfer process involved in these reactions³. The former effect has been gainfully employed to identify the perturbations in the transition state and the likely disposition of the various atoms therein⁴. Hence, a systematic kinetic study of the oxidation of a number of benzhydrols by chromium(VI) has been made in this investigation with a view to understand the topology of the transition state of these reactions.

Another interesting aspect of chromium(VI) oxidations has been the dichotomy exhibited by chromium(VI) as a one-electron or two-electron oxidant, depending on the nature of the substrate. In addition, in an elegant study involving the co-oxidation of an organic substrate and oxalic acid Roček and Hasan brought in the concept of a 'three-electron' transfer⁵. This was subsequently elaborated by a structure-reactivity study by one of the present authors⁶. The present work includes an analysis of the trends in the kinetic isotope effect in such co-oxidation reactions.

Experimental

Potassium dichromate was used as the source of chromium(VI). In the concentration range used in the present investigations ($1 - 2 \times 10^{-4} M$), it is known that the active oxidant is essentially the $HCrO_4^-$ ion. The reactions were carried out in solvent mixtures of acetic acid and water in presence of

perchloric acid (0.5–1.0 M) at temperatures between 303 and 323 K under pseudo-unimolecular conditions. The α -deuterated benzhydrols were prepared by the reduction of the corresponding benzophenones by sodium borodeutride. The isotopic purity of all the deuterated alcohols was more than 99% as confirmed by nmr and mass spectral data. The course of the oxidation reactions were monitored spectrophotometrically by following the disappearance of chromium(VI) with time at 350 nm in a Carl-Zeiss VSU-2P single beam spectrophotometer. The pseudo-first order rate constants for the oxidations were calculated from the slopes of the least square plots of $\log(A_t - A_\infty)$ versus time. The rate constants are reproducible within $\pm 2\%$.

Results and Discussions

Reactions in absence of oxalic acid: The oxidation reactions carried out in aqueous acetic acid, (50–50%, v/v) exhibit a first order dependence on both the oxidant and substrate concentrations and a dual order dependence of one or two on mineral acid concentrations. The same rate picture is also true of all the substituted benzhydrols. A rho value of -0.91 is obtained from a Hammett plot of the rate data of these benzhydrols (Tables 1 and 2). As expected, the benzhydrols exhibit a substantial kinetic isotope effect. At a given temperature and mineral acid concentration, the parent compound exhibits the maximum isotope effect followed by the other substituted benzhydrols. The temperature dependence of the KIE has been studied between 30 and 50° and the TDKIE parameters, namely, $[\Delta E_a]_D^H$ and A_H/A_D have been evaluated for three of these compounds (Tables 3–6).

Reactions in presence of oxalic acid: As was observed with the independent oxidation of benzhydrols and oxalic acid by chromium(VI) the co-

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oxidation reaction also exhibits a neat first order dependence on chromium(vi) for over 70% of the reaction. Also at a fixed concentration of oxalic acid ($8.0 \times 10^{-3} M$), it was found that the reactions exhibit

TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF RATE OF OXIDATION ON CONCENTRATION OF BENZHYDROL AND $HClO_4$

$[K_2Cr_2O_7]=1.67 \times 10^{-4} M$, Solvent=AcOH-H₂O (1:1, v/v), Temp.=30°

[Benzhydryol] × 10 ³	[HClO ₄] M	k_1 × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	k_2 × 10 ³ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
1.62	0.80	4.90	3.02
3.24	0.80	9.77	3.02
7.08	0.80	21.4	3.02
12.00	0.80	36.2	3.02
2.00	0.10	0.38	—
2.00	0.25	0.98	—
2.00	0.60	3.47	—
2.00	0.80	5.90	—
2.00	1.00	9.33	—
2.00	1.20	13.50	—

TABLE 2—SUBSTITUENT EFFECT IN OXIDATION OF BENZHYDROLS (R.C₆H₄.CHOH.C₆H₅) BY K₂Cr₂O₇

$[K_2Cr_2O_7]=1.67 \times 10^{-4} M$, Solvent=AcOH-H₂O (1:1, v/v), [ROH]= $2.01 \times 10^{-3} M$, [HClO₄]=0.8 M, Temp.=30°

R	k_2 dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
H	0.29
2-Me	0.38
4-Me	0.41
4-F	0.25
4-Cl	0.18
4-Br	0.18
3-Br	0.13

TABLE 3—SUBSTITUENT EFFECT ON KINETIC ISOTOPE EFFECT IN OXIDATION OF BENZHYDROLS (R.C₆H₄.CHOH.C₆H₅) BY K₂Cr₂O₇

$[K_2Cr_2O_7]=1.67 \times 10^{-4} M$, Solvent=AcOH-H₂O (1:1, v/v), [ROH]= $2.01 \times 10^{-3} M$, [HClO₄]=0.8 M, Temp.=30°

R	k × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	k × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	k_H/k_D
H	5.90 ± 0.06	1.13 ± 0.03	5.22
4-Cl	3.67 ± 0.05	0.73 ± 0.02	5.03
4-Me	8.23 ± 0.03	1.87 ± 0.03	4.40
4-CF ₃	3.00 ± 0.05	0.60 ± 0.01	5.00

TABLE 4—TEMPERATURE DEPENDENCE OF KINETIC ISOTOPE EFFECT IN OXIDATION OF BENZHYDROLS BY K₂Cr₂O₇

$[K_2Cr_2O_7]=1.67 \times 10^{-4} M$, Solvent=AcOH-H₂O (1:1, v/v), [ROH]= $2.01 \times 10^{-3} M$, [HClO₄]=0.8 M

R	Temp. °C	k_H × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	k_D × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	k_H/k_D
4-H	30	5.90 ± 0.06	1.13 ± 0.03	5.22
	40	11.8 ± 0.10	2.47 ± 0.03	4.78
	50	22.8 ± 0.20	5.03 ± 0.06	4.53
4-Cl	30	3.67 ± 0.05	0.73 ± 0.02	5.03
	40	7.83 ± 0.06	1.78 ± 0.03	4.40
	50	15.5 ± 0.12	3.67 ± 0.05	4.22
4-Me	30	8.23 ± 0.03	1.87 ± 0.03	4.40
	40	14.0 ± 0.12	3.57 ± 0.05	3.92
	50	25.8 ± 0.22	7.17 ± 0.06	3.60

TABLE 5—ARRHENIUS PARAMETERS FOR OXIDATION OF SUBSTITUTED BENZHYDROLS (R.C₆H₄.CHOH.C₆H₅) BY K₂Cr₂O₇

R	E_a kcal mol ⁻¹	$\Delta H^\ddagger$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$\Delta S^\ddagger$ cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta G^\ddagger$ kcal mol ⁻¹
H	13.3	12.7	-31.4	22.2
4-Cl	14.3	13.7	-29.0	22.5
4-Me	11.7	11.1	-36.0	22.0

TABLE 6—TDKIE PARAMETERS FOR OXIDATION OF SUBSTITUTED BENZHYDROLS BY K₂Cr₂O₇

	$[\Delta E_a]_D^H$ kcal mol ⁻¹	A_H/A_D
Benzhydryol	1.15	0.97
4-Chlorobenzhydryol	1.00	0.71
4-Methylbenzhydryol	1.10	0.79

a first order dependence on benzhydryol, the substituted benzhydryol and the corresponding α -deuterated derivatives. However, the co-oxidation rate exhibits a fractional order dependence (0.75) on [oxalic acid] at any fixed concentration of benzhydryol (Table 7). The value of the kinetic isotope effect is also considerably lowered in a co-oxidation reaction when compared to the normal oxidation process. The KIE is also subject to considerable variations

TABLE 7—DEPENDENCE OF RATE OF OXIDATION ON CONCENTRATION OF BENZHYDROL AND OXALIC ACID IN CO-OXIDATION REACTIONS

$[K_2Cr_2O_7]=1.67 \times 10^{-4} M$, Solvent=AcOH-H₂O (7:3, v/v), [HClO₄]=0.23 M

[Benzhydryol] × 10 ³	[OxH ₂] × 10 ³	k_1 × 10 ³ s ⁻¹	k_2 × 10 ³ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
2.01	8.00	1.66	8.27
4.00	8.00	3.32	8.30
6.00	8.00	5.00	8.38
11.00	8.00	9.12	8.29
4.00	2.01	1.17	—
4.00	4.00	1.95	—
4.00	6.00	2.63	—
4.00	8.00	3.32	—
4.00	14.10	5.01	—

because of substitution in the phenyl ring. Yet like the normal oxidation reaction, the unsubstituted benzhydryol exhibits the maximum isotope effect in the co-oxidation reactions also, followed by the 4-chloro-, 4-methyl- and 4-trimethyl benzhydryols (Table 8).

TABLE 8—KINETIC ISOTOPE EFFECT IN CO-OXIDATION REACTIONS OF BENZHYDROLS—OXALIC ACID BY K₂Cr₂O₇

$[K_2Cr_2O_7]=1.67 \times 10^{-4} M$, Solvent=AcOH-H₂O (7:3, v/v), [ROH]= $4 \times 10^{-3} M$, [OxH₂]= $8.00 \times 10^{-3} M$, [HClO₄]=0.23 M, Temp.=30°

R	k_H × 10 ³ s ⁻¹	k_D × 10 ³ s ⁻¹	k_H/k_D
4-H	3.32 ± 0.04	1.47 ± 0.02	2.26
4-Cl	2.88 ± 0.03	1.30 ± 0.01	2.22
4-Me	3.48 ± 0.05	1.62 ± 0.02	2.15
4-CF ₃	1.80 ± 0.02	1.18 ± 0.01	1.53

The major aim of the present investigation, as was stated earlier, was to understand the effect of temperature and substituents on the value of the kinetic isotope effect. Apart from the parent benzhydrol, 4-chloro-, 4-methyl- and (to a limited extent) 4-trifluoromethylbenzhydrols have been included in this study. The inclusion of the reactions of the 4-methoxy- and 4-nitrobenzhydrols would have enhanced the value of these investigations. Unfortunately spectrophotometric monitoring of the reactions of these substrates are plagued by experimental difficulties. In the case of 4-nitrobenzhydrols, both the alcohol and the product ketone absorb in the same wave length region as chromium(vi). An intensely red-coloured complex was formed with 4-methoxybenzhydrol in the presence of HClO_4 which masked the absorbance due to chromium(vi).

The well-recognised mechanistic sequence for the chromic acid oxidation of an alcohol involves the initial fast equilibrium formation of a chromate ester followed by its rate limiting decomposition in which the secondary C-H bond is cleaved. The controversy, of course, continues whether this involves the loss of the secondary hydrogen as a proton (as in an E_a mechanism) or as a hydride ion. The k_H/k_D value of 5.16 at 30° exhibited by the parent benzhydrol is somewhat less than the maximum value (6~7) expected for a centrosymmetric transition state⁷. The oxidation of isopropanol by chromium(vi) has an isotope effect of 7. If this is taken as the maximum for an unhindered secondary alcohol, the transition state for benzhydrol oxidation can be assumed to have less of 'central character' with a leaning towards the products. A polar substituent like the 4-methyl group will respond to the electron demand at the seat of the reaction, enhancing the rate and would displace the transition state further to the right. In the case of the 4-chloro substituent, and more so with the 4-trifluoromethyl group, the cleavage of the C-H bond would have just been initiated and as a consequence, these two substituents not only lower the rate but also pull the transition state towards the left. This perturbation of the transition state could have been demonstrated in a more dramatic fashion, if only the KIE studies on 4-methoxy- and 4-nitrobenzhydrols had fructified. The gradation in the isotope effect value of the four benzhydrols can be analysed further in terms of a linear free energy correlation. A plot of $\log k_H/k_D$ versus the substituent constant is found to be a 'convex-up' curve with the maximum corresponding to the unsubstituted benzhydrol. This type of correlation is not entirely unfamiliar. A similar correlation of $\log k_H/k_D$ versus pK_a was observed for various solvent polarities in the reaction of nitroethane with hydroxide ion in mixed DMSO-water solvents⁸ with a maximum around $pK_a=0$. This has been cited as an evidence for the fact that a symmetric transition state gives rise to a maximum isotope effect and a transition state perturbed from symme-

trical behaviour in either direction gives a smaller ratio.

The temperature dependence of the kinetic isotope effect gives a 'complete' picture about the topology of the transition state instead of an 'eye ball' interpretation. In the present study the values of $[\Delta E_a]_D^H$ and A_H/A_D (Tables 7 and 8) point unequivocally to a linear symmetric hydrogen transfer process (Fig. 1). According to Kwart, the restoring forces on both the sides of the hydrogen being transferred are equal or nearly so in a

Fig. 1. Normal pericyclic transition state of hydrogen transfer. Critical bonds are represented by heavy lines.

symmetrical transition state. In this case, the observed difference in the energies of activation of the protio and deuterio species would then equal the difference in the zero point energies of the two compounds, i.e. $1.0 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$. Likewise the ratio of the frequency factors varies between 0.70 and 1.42 for a symmetric transition state of a linear hydrogen transfer process.

The oxidation in the ternary system benzhydrol-oxalic acid-chromium(vi) could be regarded as composed of three independent reactions occurring simultaneously. One can thus envisage the following rate-law,

$$\begin{aligned} -\frac{d[\text{Cr}^{VI}]}{dt} &= k_1[\text{ROH}][\text{OxH}_2][\text{Cr}^{VI}] \\ &+ k_2[\text{OxH}_2]^2[\text{Cr}^{VI}] + k_3[\text{ROH}][\text{Cr}^{VI}] \\ &= k_{obs}[\text{Cr}^{VI}] \end{aligned}$$

The first term in the rate-law represents the co-oxidation process and is responsible for the observed rate increase in the alcohol oxidation in the presence of oxalic acid. The following mechanism as proposed earlier by Roček and later by us accounts for the co-oxidation route,

where, C_1 and C_2 are respectively the complexes of chromium(vi) with oxalic acid and oxalic acid-alcohol.

The increased reactivity in the co-oxidation situation has been attributed to the avoidance of formation of the unstable intermediates Cr^{IV} and Cr^V and a three-electron reduction of Cr^{VI} to Cr^{III} . Thus the transition state of the reaction would have an odd electron character and could be expected to be reflected in the isotope effect values. For, as will be evident from Table 9, two-electron oxidants

TABLE 9 COMPARATIVE KINETIC ISOTOPE EFFECT DATA FOR OXIDATION OF ALCOHOLS BY ONE- AND TWO-ELECTRON OXIDANTS

Oxidant	Substrate	k_H/k_D
Cr ^{VI}	Propan-2-ol ^a	7.0
	Cyclohexanol ^b	5.9
	Benzhydrol ^c	6.0
V ^V	Cyclohexanol ^d	4.5
	Benzhydrol ^e	4.1
Tl ^{III}	Benzhydrol ^f	6.4
Mn ^{VII}	Benzhydrol ^f	6.6
Ru ^{IV}	Propan-2-ol ^a	5.2
Ce ^{IV}	Cyclohexanol ^b	1.9
Mn ^{III}	Cyclohexanol ^d	1.6
Co ^{III}	Propan-2-ol ^j	1.4
	Cyclohexanol ^j	1.7

^aRef. 1, ^bRef. 9, ^cRef. 10, ^dRef. 11, ^eRef. 12, ^fRef. 14, ^gRef. 15, ^hRef. 16, ⁱRef. 17, ^jRef. 18.

generally yield a k_H/k_D value of 6 and one-electron oxidants often exhibit a much lower k_H/k_D ratio. The much reduced isotope effect in the co-oxidation reactions in the present study is also in accordance with the well-known reactivity-selectivity principle that increased reactivity of a system would lead to reduced selectivity. This also indicates that the C-H bond cleavage in the alcohol is in an advanced stage in these ternary systems when compared to that in the normal oxidation of alcohols.

The effect of substituents on the KIE in the co-oxidation reaction parallels the observations in the normal oxidation. The maximum value of k_H/k_D (2.26) for the unsubstituted benzhydrol is further reduced for the 4-chloro- and 4-methyl- and 4-trifluoromethylbenzhydrols (2.22, 2.15 and 1.53 respectively). Coupled with the information^g that the Hammett 'rho' for these reactions is much smaller (-0.42) consistent with a reaction that

possesses considerable radical character, the isotope effect data can be explained in terms of further perturbation of the transition state by the substituents present in the benzhydrol molecules.

Another interesting substrate that has been used in co-oxidation studies by Roček is the tertiary hydroxy acid, 2-hydroxy-2-methylbutyric acid (HMBA) which was shown to increase the oxidation rate of isopropanol considerably. Curiously, it was found that the addition of this reactant as a co-reductant (in place of oxalic acid) in the present investigation showed no variation in the rate of oxidation of benzhydrol. The prerequisite for a compound to act as a co-substrate warrants that the co-substrate should have a rate of oxidation comparable to that of the substrate. In this instance, HMBA undergoes very little oxidative decarboxylation with Cr^{VI} in comparison with the oxidation of benzhydrol and hence does not serve as a useful substrate in the co-oxidation reaction.

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